

Screening and Follow-Up of Malnourished Children Less than 5 Yrs at District Early Intervention Centre Thiruvallur

Revathy J¹, Jagadeesh Kumar D², Vijayaraj S³, Vijayalakshmi M⁴

¹Dean, GMCH, Thiruvallur

²Nodal Officer, DEIC, GMCH, Thiruvallur

³Chief Civil Surgeon, Thiruvallur

⁴Professor, Department of Community Medicine, GMCH Thiruvallur

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Vijayalakshmi M

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Malnutrition is a silent killer that is usually underreported, under addressed, and as a result under prioritized. It continues to be major cause of morbidity and mortality in children especially 6 months to 5 years. Severe acute malnutrition is a medical and social problem as it accounts for 6.4% of children below 60 months. Children after treatment at a Health facility have to be followed up to find out the outcome. This study was done to screen the under five children at District Early Intervention Centre (DEIC), GMCH, Thiruvallur for malnutrition and to follow them over a period of 24 months.

Methodology: After obtaining Institutional Ethical committee clearance, Children less than 5 years were screened for malnourishment using the standard IAP guidelines and categorised as SAM and MAM and treatment was started as per the IAP guidelines. Around 148 children were found malnourished and followed up at regular intervals for 24 months.

Results: 148 children were found to be malnourished. 75 were girls and 73 were boys. 49 of them were below 1.5 years of age, 56 were below the age of 3 years and 43 were below the age of 5 years. All of them were investigated and advised to follow the diet regime planned according to their weight and followed up at regular intervals to assess their nutrition status and any other morbidities. At the end of 24 months, there was a significant increase in the weight of all children (p value < .001, paired t-test)

Conclusion: Identifying the children with malnutrition and mere advice shall not bring about the change in nutritional status of the under-five children. Regular follow-up and continuous monitoring shall improve the Physical and Mental status of the under-five children which is the crucial age of development.

Keywords: Screening, SAM, MAM, Follow-up, Under-five Children.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Malnutrition is one of the major public health problems in India among under-five children. This is reflected by the fact that the prevalence of underweight children in India is among the highest in the world [1] It continues to be major cause of morbidity and mortality in children especially 6 months to 5 years and is mainly because of deficiency or imbalance intake of macronutrient (carbohydrate, protein, and fat) or micronutrient (vitamins, minerals, and trace element). The spectrum varies from underweight, stunted, moderately acute malnutrition, and severe acute malnutrition (SAM). Each year approximately 2.3 million deaths among 6-60 months aged children in developing countries are associated with malnutrition, which is about 41% of the total deaths in this age group.[2] It is important for the health system to detect malnutrition at an early stage for

planning and implementing timely interventions at the community level. The WHO protocol for the management of SAM states that after discharge from treatment programmes, children should be periodically monitored to avoid relapse. All SAM children should be followed up by health providers till s/he reaches weight-for-height of -1 SD.

The frequency of follow-up is as follows:

- 7 days after discharge
- Fortnightly in first month, then
- Monthly thereafter until WHZ reaches -1 SD or above.

If problem is found, visit should be more frequent until it is resolved

The challenges in follow-up and outcome are not much studied and hence this study is done to follow

the malnourished children attending DEIC, GMCH, Thiruvallur.

Materials and Methods:

After obtaining the Ethical clearance from the institution, a Hospital –based longitudinal study was conducted among malnourished under five children detected by screening at DEIC, GMCH, Thiruvallur.

Operational definition as per WHO for Malnutrition:

- **Moderate acute malnutrition (MAM)**, defined as weight-for-height z-score (WHZ) between -2 and -3 or mid-upper arm circumference (MUAC) between 115 millimeters and <125 millimeters
- **Severe acute malnutrition (SAM)**, defined as WHZ < -3 or MUAC < 115 millimeters, or the presence of bilateral pitting edema, or both
- **Global acute malnutrition (GAM)** refers to MAM and SAM together; it is used as a measurement of nutritional status at a population level and as an indicator of the severity of an emergency situation
- **Malnutrition** is assessed by weight for age for under-five children.[3]

Study Population: Under five children of both gender who are malnourished.

Study Area:

DEIC, GMCH, Thiruvallur which serves to prevent and treat various deformities in children at the District Level including Congenital anomalies among children, Rehabilitative therapy for spastic children and autism.

Sample Size: With the prevalence of 6.4% of SAM from previous studies [4],

Sample size calculated using the formula,

$$N = Z^2 P Q / d^2$$

- Z= 1.96

- P= 6.4
- Q = 93.6
- d (absolute precision)= 5%

$$N = 1.96^2 * 6.4 * 93.6 / 25 = 94 \text{ (at 95\% Confidence interval)}$$

Adding 25% as non-response rate, 94 + 16 = 110

Sample size = 110 (Required sample). 148 children were picked up in screening and all of them were studied.

Study duration: 24 months (May 2022- April 2024)

Inclusion criteria:

1. All under five children attending DEIC
2. Children of those parents giving consent

Exclusion criteria: Children with any other co morbidities or acute illness

Methodology:

Children attending DEIC were screened for Malnutrition with height and weight measurements by Simple random sampling method using the IAP Standard guidelines after obtaining informed consent from the parent accompanying them and socio - demographic details were obtained from them. They were given treatment for any morbidity found and Nutritional intervention measures that can be followed at home were advised. They were asked to bring the child for follow-up or in case of any morbidities.

The field staff were sensitized and involved in the follow-up of children at home. At the end of 24 months, they were again weighed and the data was entered in Microsoft Excel and analysed using SPSS-16 Version.

Results and Discussion:

Number of Children studied was 148 .Among them 75 were girls and 73 were boys representing no difference in the gender.

Table 1: AGE Distribution

No	Age (yrs)	Number of Children
1.	< 1.5	49(33%)
2.	1.5-3	56(38%)
3	>3	43(29%)

Mean age was 2.2yrs with a standard deviation of (+/-)1.24. More number of children less than 3yrs was malnourished which could be attributed to the Improper Breast feeding practices, improper weaning and infections. Children more than 3 years have access to the Balwadi centres which provide Nutritional supplementation for children with 500 Kcal /Day and protein 12-15 g/day. [5] A study by Ramachandran and Gopalan found that there was a progressive increase in under-weight

and stunting rates between 3 and 23 months of age;[3] thus, the service component should be strengthened, especially for under two children with respect to exclusive breast feeding, supplementary feeding practices, regular growth monitoring, prevention of infections, immunization, health and nutrition education of mothers with necessary follow-up, and corrective actions. At the grass root level, planning and integration of the work of Anganwadi workers

under Integrated Child Development Service (ICDS), Accredited Social Health Activists (ASHA) under National Rural Health Mission and

active community participation will result in better delivery of services to target groups.

Table 2: Significance in weight gain

	Mean Wt	Standard deviation	t	P value
Before	8.25	2.23	-13.988	<.0001
After	9.19	2.32		

Almost all of the children showed an increase in weight gain.

Mothers' education and interest to bring the children for regular follow up were contributory for the improvement in child's weight gain earlier.

Current WHO management protocols are public-health focused and include:

- An emphasis on high programme coverage
- Early identification of affected children,
- Allowing those with an appetite and who are clinically stable (i.e. 'uncomplicated' SAM) to be managed as outpatients using Ready-to-Use Therapeutic Food (RUTF);
- Inpatient care for the much smaller number of children with additional medical complications.

This 'Community-Management of Acute Malnutrition' (CMAM) model of care is cost-effective, allows for increased caseloads, and is now supported by substantial evidence of having contributed to lower mortality rates from SAM.[6]

Acknowledgement:

We acknowledge the staff of DEIC for their contribution

References:

1. World Bank. India, Undernourished children: A call for reform and action. Available from: <http://web.worldbank.org>
2. Schroeder DG, Brown KH. Nutritional status as a predictor of child survival: Summarizing the association and quantifying its global impact. Bull World Health Organ 1994; 72: 569-79.
3. Ramachandran P, Gopalan HS. Assessment of nutritional status in Indian preschool children using WHO 2006 Growth Standards. Indian J Med Res 2011; 134:47-53.
4. Ajeet Singh Bhadoria et al Prevalence of severe acute malnutrition and associated socio-demographic factors among children aged 6 months-5 years in rural population of Northern India: A population-based survey J Family Med Prim Care. 2017 Apr-Jun; 6(2): 380-385
5. A.H.Suryakantha Community Medicine with recent advances, pg 612.
6. Collins S. Community-based therapeutic care-a new paradigm for selective feeding in nutritional crises. London: Overseas Development Institution; 2004.
7. World Health Organisation. Guideline: Updates on the management of severe acute malnutrition in infants and children. Geneva; 20
8. World Health Organisation, United Nations Children's Fund. WHO child growth standards and the identification of severe acute malnutrition in infants and children. Geneva; 2009.
9. Lindsey Lenters, Kerri Wazny, and Zulfiqar A Bhutta. Management of Severe and Moderate Acute Malnutrition in Children- Reproductive, Maternal, Newborn, and Child Health: Disease Control Priorities, Third Edition (Volume 2).
10. Swaroop Kumar Sahu, S. Ganesh Kumar, B. Vishnu Bhat et al, Malnutrition among under-five children in India and strategies for control, Journal of Natural Science, Biology and Medicine | January 2015 | Vol 6 | Issue 1.